

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF COCHLEAR IMPLANTING IN THE EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING DEFECTS

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A number of positive changes that have taken place in the field of medicine and education in recent years are closely related to the unification of the activities of representatives of various fields in new directions in solving the issues of the fate of children with developmental problems. Early diagnosis of deviations from the norm in the child's development, elimination of the consequences of the problem, rehabilitation, providing pedagogical support to children of early and younger ages with developmental problems in one way or another, and developing models of integration into general education institutions remains one of the urgent problems on the agenda.

It is known that in the modern education system, the idea of inclusive education and the issues of its implementation in the conditions of our republic have been one of the topics that have been raised rapidly in recent years. Nowadays, Jurli-district hearing aids (devices) (OKA) are used to restore the hearing of people with hearing problems of various degrees. In cases of high degree of sensorineural hearing loss and deafness, due to some technical, physiological, pathophysiological reasons, such devices slightly improve speech sound perception, but in most cases, they do not allow it at all.

In recent years, the positive solution of the problem of early and childhood disabilities at the world level is closely related to the integration of the activities of representatives of different fields in new directions in solving the issues of the fate of these children. Research in the field of deaf audiology (from the Latin words *surdus* - deaf and *audio* - hearing), the introduction of new technologies into it, the integration of the activities of scientists from different directions in this process, a new method of improving the hearing perception of people with profound hearing problems - multichannel cochlear implantation enabled the development of the method. Cochlear implantation is a medical procedure that involves surgically connecting the afferent fibers of the auditory nerves located in the inner ear (in the inner part of the ear) to the afferent fibers of the auditory nerve in order to restore hearing sensations. Sensorineural hearing loss is mainly manifested by damage to the inner ear, that is, to its hair-like tissues. However, despite significant damage to the sensory tissue, the fibers of the auditory nerve are preserved in the majority of such patients, and they are able to deliver signals that provide the formation of auditory sensations to the brain with the help of direct electric current. The operation of the cochlear implant, which can be considered as an artificial inner ear, is based on this principle, and it is a multi-functional system from simple sound amplification devices, which not only restores hearing, but also provides melodious and natural sounds. differs from Nowadays, it is becoming more and more common for many people living in many countries to recover their hearing with the help of cochlear implants. For more than forty years, surgical operations for the restoration of hearing with the help of cochlear implantation have been carried out by experts from Australia, the USA, Austria, Germany, France, Japan and Russia. It is worth noting that cochlear implantation is a very complex device in terms of structure, so its production requires a lot of money, and naturally, such operations are among the expensive measures. Therefore, in advanced countries, where humanitarian ideas such as guaranteeing the child's developmental rights and educational needs are set as priority tasks, such activities are under the control of official agencies, the funds of the state, local budget, various foundations and sponsoring organizations are used. is being implemented with the involvement of

Hearing restoration with cochlear implantation includes three stages:

1. Pre-operative stage. This stage includes comprehensive diagnostic examination, otological examination, audiological examination, vestibulometry, computer tomography, electrodiagnostic examination of the brain, general medical examination and psychoneurological examination, as well as psychological preparation for surgery (other clients with cochlear implants by getting acquainted with) covers such activities as

2. Stage of surgical operation.

3. Post-operative stage. This stage is called the post-operative rehabilitation stage, and it requires more time than the previous two stages, 80% of the work allocated for the general event should be carried out in this period, and the event held during this period is more complex, and requires greater responsibility. It is distinguished by the fact that it plays an important role in the child's development, socialization, and integration into society.

Because after the operation, hearing adjustment by audiologists, development of auditory attention by deaf pedagogues, training of children's speech, which are carried out consistently, are an important factor in the integration of people with cochlear implants into social life.

It is known that the idea of inclusive education in the modern education system and its implementation in the conditions of our republic is one of the topics that are frequently addressed. In the world deaf-pedagogical practice, in particular, Russian scientists I.V. Koroleva, V.I. Pudov, O.V. Zontova, O.S. Zhukova, E.V. Mironova, etc. As a result of the practical-corrective-pedagogical work carried out by the Ministry of Education and Culture, restoring the hearing of children with hearing problems with KI or KI, assimilating them to general education institutions, society, i.e., returning them to the society of "hearing people", is another effective alternative to achieve their perfection. has been proven several times. It is confirmed that the involvement of a wide range of specialists (medical staff, audiologist, psychologist, defectologist, etc.), as well as family members of the client (patient) in therapeutic and correctional-pedagogical work is an important factor that ensures the success of the result.

References:

1. Xamidova, M. U. (2018). Maxsus pedagogika. T-2013 "Fan va texnologiyalar nashiryoti.
2. Nomozova, M. (2023). Korreksion (maxsus) pedagogikaning asosiy vazifalari, tamoyillari va metodlari. Talqin va tadqiqotlar, 1(7).
3. Rimbayeva, O. B. (2023). Maxsus pedagogika fanining rivojlanish tendentsiyalari. Scholar, 1(23), 33-36.
4. Nizomova, M. B. (2023). Narrow and broad interpretation of the contact concept of "pedagogical language" in the social environment of terms related to pedagogy in english and uzbek languages. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 5(05), 93-99.
5. Nematov, O. (2023, September). Ecotourism potential of the jizzakh region. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 138-142).